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“THE NUMBER 2”

Two hands weaving together, a promise to begin,

On July 2nd, with the sun shining.

Two hearts murmured, "This love is true."

The journey began, just us two.

Two steps forward with no sight of fear.

With laughter and tears and through day and night.

Two souls bonded by the grip of fate,

Love in motion could never be late.

Two voices singing in harmony,

A melody born underneath the moon gleam.

Forever etched, this date so cherished,

The Second of July, sincere love.